

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF FACEBOOK BRAND-RELATED USER GENERATED CONTENT (UGC) ON CONSUMER RESPONSES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to propose and test a model that investigates the impact of brand related Facebook UGC on consumer responses. Research objectives include: Understand the impact of brand related UGC with respect to consumer emotional & cognitive responses, Investigate the process by which these cognitive and emotional responses are impacted, and Test whether homophily and brand involvement have any moderating impact on these proposed relationships. SOR Model has been used to drive the proposed model for this study (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). The SOR model studies the impact of environmental elements on consumer responses; there responses may include behavior, emotion and cognition. Data collection for this research will be done through online survey questionnaires. These questionnaires will be shared online to potential respondents. These questionnaires will also contain a link to dummy Facebook Fan Pages that will work as stimuli, then after being exposed to these stimuli will the respondent be asked the required questions. The respondents will be selected through Purposive Sampling who have the characteristics of being a regular Facebook user and have exposure to E-Commerce. The data of this research will be analyzed through SPSS and AMOS to confirm reliability and validity of our constructs and to test our model.

Keywords: Social Commerce, Stimuli Organism Response Model, Social Media, E-commerce, S-O-R, SEM-PLS, Homophily, Brand Involvement, Social Networking Sites, SNS, Purchase Intention, Consumer Responses, Facebook

JEL Codes: D91, L81

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this chapter is to discuss the background of social media in the retail industry and how social media is used by customers. The Objective and Significance of this research are also discussed.

1.1. BACKGROUND

With the adaption of new technology, the retail industry is on the verge of changing rapidly. Technological Advancements have played a major role in improving operations and customer relations in retail industry (Accenture, 2013). There has been a drastic change in consumer experience due to technology. There have been a significant reduction in barriers towards adopting a technological tool as a part of lifestyle, and that has resulted in technology users of many ages and backgrounds (Accenture, 2013), this usage of digital medium allows consumers to take full control of their purchasing experiences. Getting information about any product and purchasing has become easier than ever. According to a google survey (Google, 2013), about cell phone user by consumers, 82 % of 1,507 shoppers looked for product information via their smartphones in-between shopping and 90% used smartphones to compare prices and product information prior to shopping.

With the latest technologies changing consumer behavior in the retail industry, the impact of social media is also significant. There are many social media platforms that enable consumers to interact and share experiences, which impact their buying intention (Tuten, 2008). These social media platforms include Social Networking Sites (SNSs), wikis, online forums, blogs, micro blogs, and other content sharing online platforms. SNSs allow people to search for

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and find people of similar likings and mindset, and enable social communication (Joinson, 2008). Wikis are type of SNS that are designed to allow all customers to collectively participate and update information on wikis (Heinonen, 2011). Micro-blogs and blogs have content shared in a free writing style by customers and organizations both. Other platforms may include content sharing platforms that may include content that is visual in nature (videos and pictures) (Heinonen, 2011). Everybody is able to participate in these social networking sites and share related content (Tuten, 2008).

1.2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Social media platforms allow participants to share their views about certain brand; this content containing their experiences has an influence on other participants as well. This impact need to be examined and understood. There has been limited research conducted on the impact of user generated content (UGC) on consumer intention and behavior; so, this research aims to conduct a research on the impact of brand related UGC on customer response. Understanding the role of UGC is very crucial, as it is considered to have a significant impact on customer response and it also presents a great challenge because lack of research has led to lack of understanding in controlling its impact. Empirical research is also important for better understanding of how

Consumers are using UGC, resulting in a shift of focus from market to consumers. This addresses the impact of UGC and its extent of impact due to which consumer response is influenced.

All social media platforms differ in the way they enable participants to get and share information with others via UGC. This research specifically focuses on Facebook, as it is one of the most used social media platforms and provides a variety of ways to share and consume UGC. A broad approach is taken to understand the impact of UGC on consumer behavior. This broad approach involves testing of SOR consumer response model (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). For this research, the main focus is on the investigation of impact of brand related UGC on customer response specifically on Facebook a eWOM. So, the two main characteristics of eWOM were also included as moderation variables that are homophily and brand involvement from the theory of communication (Hovland et al., 1953).

1.3. SIGNIFICANCE

Based on the given questions, cover both theoretical and practical aspects. This research has added theoretical understanding towards the impact of UGC on consumer response. This consumer response will help brands to better understand the best way to use brand related UGC. Studying the role of homophily and brand involvement will help the marketers to better understand how brand related UGC impacts consumer response. Following this research, the marketers are able to better understand how UGC impacts different characteristics of consumer behavior; this would allow them to use UGC in a more strategically effective way.

Prior work done on eWOM was followed to build a theoretical standing, then the study extended this theory into social media context and examining the impact of eWOM on consumer response specifically in social media perspective, then a process was documented to explain this impact (Kim, 2014). The proposed model was the first to present this process of brand related UGC impacting consumer response derived from S O R Model (Kim, 2014).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review covers the theoretical framework being tested, the related theory for the framework, and hypotheses being tested in this research (Kim, 2014).

2.1. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1.1. STIMULUS ORGANISM RESPONSE (SOR) FRAMEWORK

The SOR model was initially designed to depict the impact of environment on behavioral responses (cognitive and emotional). The SOR model depicts that the relationship between its three main constructs in linear with the mediating role of organism between stimuli and response (Kihlstrom, 1987).

Stimulus: In SOR model, the construct stimuli relates to the physical environment that influences an individual's internal (Eroglu et al., 2001; Sherman et al., 1997). In regard to this model, many stimulus have been tested; for example, color (Bellizzi et al., 1983; Bellizzi & Hite, 1992), lights (Baker et al., 1992), music (Baker et al., 1992), as factors that influence a consumers behavior.

Organism: In SOR model, organism is the construct that mediates the relationship between stimuli and response (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). Mehrabian & Russell in 1974 proposed that organism involves pleasure, arousal and

dominance. Pleasure represents happiness, arousal represents state of being active, and dominance is to state of not restrictions (Breneman & Geuens, 2004; Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). Based on many follow-up researches, arousal and emotion have been found to be emotional responses as dominance has little or no empirical evidence (Donovan & Rossiter, 1982). Response: The response in SOR model represents the final outcome reactions (Bagozzi, 1986).

Figure 1. SOR model (Eroglu et al., 2001)

2.2. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The focus of this research is on the impact of brand related UGC on Facebook on consumer behavior. So, the hypotheses have been designed in this context. Anjella J. in 2014 investigated the same hypotheses on the basis of which, a grounded level theory was built in UGC domain (KIM, 2014). This research attempts to retest them in a different context to authenticate the credibility of the theory previously generate.

2.2.1. ORGANISMIC RESPONSES TO BRAND-RELATED UGC: S-O RELATIONSHIPS

H1. Consumer emotional responses are influenced by UGC related to Brand.

H1-a. Pleasure is influenced by UGC related to Brand.

H1-b. Arousal is influenced by UGC related to Brand.

H2. Perceived Information Quality responses are influenced by UGC related to Brand.

2.2.2. BEHAVIORAL RESPONSES TO BRAND-RELATED UGC: O-R RELATIONSHIPS

H3. Information Pass-along is positively influenced by emotional response.

H3-a. Information Pass-along is positively influenced by Pleasure.

H3-b. Information Pass-along is positively influenced by Arousal.

H4. Information Pass-along is positively influenced by cognitive response.

H5. Impulse buying is positively influenced by emotional response.

H5-a. Impulse buying is positively influenced by Pleasure.

H5-b. Impulse buying is positively influenced by Arousal.

H6. Impulse buying is positively influenced by cognitive response.

H7. Future-purchase intention is positively influenced by emotional response.

H7-a. Future-purchase intention is positively influenced by Pleasure.

H7-b. Future-purchase intention is positively influenced by Arousal.

H8. Future-purchase intention is positively influenced by cognitive response.

H9. Brand engagement is positively influenced by emotional response.

H9-a. Brand engagement is positively influenced by Pleasure.

H9-b. Brand engagement is positively influenced by Arousal.

H10. Brand engagement is positively influenced by cognitive response.

2.2.3. MODERATION

H11. Relationships between consumer internal states and UGC is moderated by Homophily.

H11. Relationships between consumer internal states and UGC is moderated by BrandInvolvement.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. PHILOSOPHICAL UNDERPINNING OF RESEARCH

For online buying, customer intention to purchase is researched to be impacted by user generated content (UGC) or customer feedback on online platforms; these platforms include all social media platforms where customers may engage in a discussion regarding their opinion on an online purchase of a product or service. These discussions provide feedback, comments, ratings, and customer ranking etc.

This research focuses on understanding the impact of customer feedback on social media platforms on consumer buying intention. The data is collected through online questionnaire forms. The participants are social media users, who have experience with conducting purchase online. We follow Post-positivism theory for this research; Positivism argues that only observable and measurable entities are a part of knowledge and reality, and everything beyond that is impossible. That means that human emotions and thoughts would also be considered as not a part of human decision-making process, as we can't directly observe and measure these. Online survey makes it possible to generate a simulation that properly represents the phenomenon of interest. As the main objective of this research is to investigate the impact of UGC in SNS on Consumer response, an exposure to an online UGC is expected to impact the response from consumer and so a stimulus was also introduced during online questionnaire survey; Because of this, online survey was the right methodology for this research. On the other hand, Post-positivism follows the concepts of critical realism, which states that there is much more the reality that what we can observe. This means, that emotions and thoughts are also a part of the reality and are observable and measurable to an extent. Now these observations do not represent reality itself but

help us in understanding it, as post-positivism argues that fully understanding reality is not possible.

3.2. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study was conducted through an online Questionnaire Survey. The purpose of this survey is to get quantitative behavioral responses from the respondents that will allow the researchers to make interference regarding the respondents using this data (Creswell, 2009). World-wide, the rate of online survey method is growing significantly (Comley, 2003). Compared to all traditional methods, online surveys allow much larger reach, quicker response rate, and much more cost effectiveness (Sue & Ritter, 2011). This type of surveys allow researchers to accumulate large data and easily transfer it to any other research tool (Duffy et al., 2005). This method of online survey is also proven to be convenient for respondents. This way, the questionnaire can be filled at time and place of choice and convenience. Because the online questionnaire survey is filled in privacy and in the absence of the researcher, their possible biases of the researcher is eliminated (Duffy et al., 2005; Duffy, 2005).

3.3. INSTRUMENT DEVELOPMENT

3.3.1. DEVELOPING A VISUAL-STIMULI

In order to examine the impact of UGC on consumer response, stimulus Facebook SNS fan pages were made along with relevant postings. Fan pages allow customers of a certain brand to share their experiences of that brand and interact with each other in-order to make an informed decision regarding a purchase. Fan page is a platform where firms can directly communicate with its customers and consumers; because of this reason, the concept of eWOM can also be analyzed through this medium (Chen et al., 2013). There are many fan pages of Facebook that allow customers to post their experiences with the brand and respond through comments to other customers.

3.3.2. QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT

Online questionnaire that has been used for this research has been adapted (Kim, 2014).

3.4. SAMPLING

All respondents of this research are active users of Facebook, one of the most well-known and used SNSs for the purpose of sharing experiences. According to Smith (2014), more than 65% of internet users are also Facebook users (Wildrich, 2013). Comparing all age brackets, the most concentration is found in the age bracket of 18 – 27. Based on these research base facts, Criteria for respondent was to be a Facebook user and of age above 18. Purpose sampling technique was used.

3.5. DATA COLLECTION

Online questionnaire survey is being used to gather data from respondents. The questionnaire will be circulated to university students of 3 well-known universities in Karachi city. The questions are 7 – Scale Unipolar likert Scale. For gathering demographics, there are open ended questions in order to get a deeper insight into respondents' background.

3.6. DATA ANALYSIS

In order to test our proposed model, SPSS and AMOS are being used for statistical analysis of collected data. Descriptive and frequency analysis are conducted on SPSS to determine the demographic characteristics. Independent sample T-test is being used in this study to analyze the difference of brand awareness between the two brands being analyzed. For testing validity and reliability, correlation, reliability tests, and factor analysis are conducted. Structural equation modeling (SEM) is being used in this data analysis as it allows simultaneous examination between multiple independent and dependent variables. SEM is being used here for analyzing direct and indirect paths.

4. ANALYSIS

4.1. BRAND AWARENESS INDEPENDENT T-TESTS

Table 1: Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
	F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean-Differ	Std.Error- Differ
Equal variances assumed	14.352	.000	59.587	398	.000	3.89250	.06532
Unequal variances not assumed			59.587	370.97	.000	3.89250	.06532

(Stylo m = 6.2, Borjan m = 2.3; t = 59.587, df = 371, p = .000)

This shows that brand awareness level between the 2 brands is significantly different. One brand has high brand involvement and other has low brand involvement.

4.2. PILOT TEST: UGC CONTENT DIMENSIONS

Table 2

Construct	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
	RM1	400	4	7	5.86	.913
	RM2	400	4	7	5.92	.892
UGC Message	RM3	400	4	7	5.87	.925
	EM1	400	4	7	5.86	.939
	EM2	400	4	7	5.91	.944
	EM3	400	4	7	5.83	.950

This confirms that UGC item stimuli are good for use to be used as stimuli for this research.

4.3. PILOT TEST: EFA OF RELIABILITIES

Table 3

Construct	No. of Items	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cronbach's Alpha
UGC	6	3.39	6.78	0.82
PL	6	3.27	6.54	0.91
AR	6	3.19	6.39	0.77
IQ	4	3.02	6.04	0.74
PA	5	3.01	6.03	0.72
IB	2	2.64	5.28	0.48
FP	5	2.61	5.22	0.73
BE	6	2.44	4.88	0.82
HM	4	2.24	4.48	0.78
BI	6	1.61	3.23	0.77

The cronbach's alphas show that the constructs have a strong convergent reliability. This is a pilot test done from first 50 responses.

4.4. DEMOGRAPHICS

Table 4

Description	Frequency
Gender	
Women	121
Men	79
Age	
18-24	80
25-34	30
35-44	43
45-54	27
55 and up	10
Marital Status	
Married	111
Divorced	12
Single	77
Education	
High school or less	53
Technical school	72
Some college	24
College graduate	28
Master's degree	43
Household Income	
Under 20,000 Rs	43
\$20,000- \$39,999	65
\$60,000-\$79,999 89 16.7	51
\$80,000-\$99,999 63 11.8	30
Over \$100,000 54 10.1	11

4.5. FACEBOOK ACTIVITIES

Table 5

Characteristic	Frequency
Frequency of Facebook Use	
Continuously	33
Multiple times/day	54
Once/day	25
Couple of times/week	41
Once/week	23
Occasionally	26
Missing	4
Reasons for Use	
Stay in touch	20
Expression	48
Making connections	52
General Information	11
Surveillance	22
Entertainment	37
Keeping in touch with people	10
Number of Brands Following	
None	51
1-10	21
10-50	68
50-100	44
100 or over	16
Missing	0
Number of Fashion Brands Following	
None	24
1-10	59
10-50	71
50-100	3
100 or over	10
Missing	1
Created UGC related to brand Posting	
Yes	79
No	121
Missing	0
UGC related to brand Posting	
Site	
Brand fan pages	29
Personal wall page	69
Type	
Narrative form	10
Photos of consumption	33
Likes (“liking” a brand)	45

4.6. RESULTS: T-TESTS

Table 6

Construct & Items	Mean		T-test (df = 378)	Construct & Items	Mean		T-test (df = 378)
	Style	Borjan			Style	Borjan	
Brand Involvement				Pleasure			
BI1	3.2	2.9	0.3	PL1	5.1	5.0	0.1
BI2	2.9	2.8	0.1	PL2	4.9	5.2	-0.3
BI3	3.4	3.2	0.2	PL3	4.8	5.0	-0.2
BI4	3.1	2.6	0.5	PL4	5.3	5.1	0.2
BI5	3.2	2.7	0.5	PL5	4.8	4.6	0.2
BI6	3.4	2.9	0.5	PL6	5.2	4.9	0.3
Information Pass-along				Arousal			
PA1	5.2	5.0	0.2	AR1	3.8	4.2	-0.4
PA2	5.2	5.2	0	AR2	4.6	4.3	0.3
PA3	5.0	5.1	-0.1	AR3	3.9	4.3	-0.4
PA4	5.1	5.0	0.1	AR4	4.5	4.6	-0.1
PA5	5.1	5.1	0	AR5	4.1	4.2	-0.1
Impulse Buying				AR6	4.0	3.9	0.1
IB1	4.1	4.3	-0.2	Information Quality			
IB2	3.8	3.8	0	IQ1	4.2	4.1	0.1
Future Purchase Intention				IQ2	3.8	4.0	-0.2
FP1	4.1	4.1	0	IQ3	3.7	3.9	-0.2
FP2	4.3	4.5	-0.2	IQ4	4.1	4.3	-0.2
FP3	4.4	4.1	0.3	UGC Message			
FP4	4.7	4.5	0.2	RM1	3.4	3.2	0.2
FP5	4.2	4.3	-0.1	RM2	3.1	2.6	0.5
Brand Engagement				RM3	3.2	2.7	0.5
BE1	4.2	4.1	0.1	EM1	3.4	2.9	0.5
BE2	3.8	4.0	-0.2	EM2	3.8	4.0	-0.2
BE3	3.7	3.9	-0.2	EM3	3.7	3.9	-0.2
BE4	4.1	4.3	-0.2	Brand Involvement			
BE5	3.9	4.0	-0.1	BI1	5.0	4.1	0.9
BE6	4.1	3.8	0.3	BI2	5.2	3.9	1.3
Homophily				BI3	5.0	4.0	1
HM1	3.8	4.0	-0.2	BI4	5.1	3.9	1.2
HM2	3.7	3.9	-0.2	BI5	4.6	4.3	0.3
HM3	4.1	4.3	-0.2	BI6	4.9	4.0	0.9
HM4	3.9	4.0	-0.1				

The difference between the t-test values for two brands is quite close. This signifies that items used in these constructs are all valid.

4.7. NORMALITY OF PRIMARY DATA

Table 7

Items	Mean	Std.	Skewness	Kurtosis
BI1	5.87	.899	-.412	-.605
BI2	5.84	.919	-.368	-.707
BI3	5.92	.893	-.389	-.689
BI4	5.95	.947	-.464	-.796
BI5	5.90	.971	-.410	-.897
BI6	5.88	.949	-.382	-.847
PA1	5.88	.929	-.382	-.774
PA2	5.85	.909	-.277	-.823
PA3	5.94	.925	-.467	-.694
PA4	5.85	.906	-.340	-.727
PA5	5.83	.941	-.355	-.799
IB1	5.90	.867	-.315	-.694
IB2	5.87	.942	-.384	-.798
FP1	5.85	.881	-.332	-.646
FP2	5.86	.934	-.385	-.760
FP3	5.86	.949	-.431	-.737
P4	5.86	.943	-.359	-.838
FP5	5.87	.917	-.466	-.580
BE1	5.79	.950	-.256	-.912
BE2	5.89	.935	-.388	-.800
BE3	5.82	.956	-.307	-.901
BE4	5.87	.893	-.417	-.567
BE5	5.90	.933	-.456	-.691
BE6	5.86	.922	-.389	-.707
PL1	5.88	.943	-.402	-.788
PL2	5.82	.925	-.259	-.862
PL3	5.89	.915	-.455	-.617
PL4	5.86	.985	-.369	-.956
PL5	5.90	.930	-.472	-.646
PL6	5.84	.862	-.262	-.673
AR1	5.86	.938	-.390	-.762
AR2	5.93	.880	-.435	-.564
AR3	5.88	.896	-.371	-.671
AR4	5.89	.954	-.405	-.836
AR5	5.89	.957	-.443	-.789
AR6	5.87	.914	-.413	-.655
IQ1	5.88	.944	-.410	-.782
IQ2	5.89	.877	-.343	-.665
IQ3	5.84	.963	-.370	-.857
IQ4	5.88	.956	-.375	-.875
RM1	5.86	.913	-.365	-.725
RM2	5.92	.892	-.448	-.586
RM3	5.87	.925	-.370	-.765
EM1	5.86	.939	-.344	-.842
EM2	5.91	.944	-.470	-.722
EM3	5.83	.950	-.315	-.874
HM1	5.86	.920	-.466	-.578
HM2	5.87	.896	-.355	-.689
HM3	5.88	.981	-.381	-.948
HM4	5.86	.933	-.300	-.894

4.8. RELIABILITY OF MEASURES

Table 8

Construct	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients
UGC	6	0.82
PL	6	0.91
AR	6	0.77
IQ	4	0.74
PA	5	0.72
IB	2	0.68
FP	5	0.73
BE	6	0.62
HM	4	0.78
BI	6	0.77

The cronbach's alphas show that the constructs have a strong convergent reliability.

4.9. CORRELATION OF VARIABLES

Table 9

	BI	PA	IB	FP	BE	PL	AR	IQ	UGC	HM
BI	1	.757**	.507**	.491**	.544**	.527**	.555**	.555**	.513**	.496**
PA	.757**	1	.547**	.527**	.529**	.522**	.607**	.600**	.534**	.520**
IB	.507**	.547**	1	.446**	.521**	.482**	.522**	.483**	.491**	.522**
FP	.491**	.527**	.446**	1	.515**	.489**	.505**	.505**	.503**	.474**
BE	.544**	.529**	.521**	.515**	1	.531**	.562**	.536**	.520**	.563**
PL	.527**	.522**	.482**	.489**	.531**	1	.520**	.509**	.503**	.538**
AR	.555**	.607**	.522**	.505**	.562**	.520**	1	.548**	.476**	.494**
IQ	.555**	.600**	.483**	.505**	.536**	.509**	.548**	1	.511**	.562**
UGC	.513**	.534**	.491**	.503**	.520**	.503**	.476**	.511**	1	.544**
HM	.496**	.520**	.522**	.474**	.563**	.538**	.494**	.562**	.544**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results showed that correlation between PA and BI exceeded .85, however the two variables were included in the model as response variables. The high correlation between these two variables does not create estimation problems in SEM.

4.10. GOODNESS-OF-FIT STATISTICS FOR ITEM SETS

Table 10

Construct	Full Item Set		Reduced Item Set	
	No. of Items	Model Fit Stats.	No. of Items	Model Fit Stats.
Arousal	6	$X^2 = 298.00$ $df = 9$ $p = .00$ $CFI = .85$	2	$X^2 = 121.00$ $df = 5$ $p = .00$ $CFI = .93$
Information Quality	4	$X^2 = 182.00$ $df = 5$ $p = .00$ $CFI = .71$	3	$X^2 = 68.00$ $df = 2$ $p = .00$ $CFI = .94$
IP	6	$X^2 = 231.00$ $df = 10$ $p = .00$ $CFI = .95$	5	$X^2 = 71.00$ $df = 3$ $p = .00$ $CFI = .97$

Goodness of fit tells you if your sample data represents the data you would expect to find in the actual population. A structural analysis was conducted using the maximum likelihood estimation method. The results from the

structural model are presented. The structural model exhibited a good fit. CFI Improved, X² reduced closer to 0.

4.11. RELIABILITY

Table 11

Construct	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients
UGC	6	0.82
PL	6	0.91
AR	2	0.89
IQ	3	0.77
PA	4	0.81
IB	2	0.48
FP	5	0.73
BE	6	8.22
HM	4	0.78
BI	6	0.77

Reliability improved after reduction of 4 items.

4.12. MEASUREMENT MODEL EVALUATION: STANDARDIZATION LOADINGS

Table 12

Construct	No. of Items	Standardized Loadings (min -max)
UGC	6	.80 - .88
PL	6	.93 - .96
AR	2	.89 - .92
IQ	3	.91 - .95
PA	4	.70 - .87
IB	2	.82 - .85
FP	5	.87 - .92
BE	6	.93 - .95
HM	4	.80 - .88
BI	6	.95 - .95

An indicator that almost perfectly reflects the latent variable (e.g., " Brand-related UGC influences pleasure") thus should very highly correlate with the latent variable "PL" (Would expect at least .80-.90). Other indicators that are conceptually more distant from the supposed latent variable could result in a lower loading.

4.13. RESULTS: MEASUREMENT MODEL

Table 13

	PA	IB	FP	BE	PL	AR	IQ	UGC
PA	1	.553**	.521**	.527**	.500**	.532**	.557**	.502**
IB	.553**	1	.446**	.521**	.482**	.502**	.471**	.491**
FP	.521**	.446**	1	.515**	.489**	.511**	.524**	.503**
BE	.527**	.521**	.515**	1	.531**	.543**	.545**	.520**
PL	.500**	.482**	.489**	.531**	1	.498**	.532**	.503**
AR	.532**	.502**	.511**	.543**	.498**	1	.573**	.518**
IQ	.557**	.471**	.524**	.545**	.532**	.573**	1	.539**
UGC	.502**	.491**	.503**	.520**	.503**	.518**	.539**	1
Reliability	0.83	0.91	0.90	0.88	0.82	0.79	0.92	0.87

4.14. CFA: MEASUREMENT MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

4.15. DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY OF MEASUREMENT MODEL

Table 14

	PA	IB	FP	BE	PL	AR	IQ	UGC
PA	0.59							
IB	.553**	0.67						
FP	.521**	.446**	0.68					
BE	.527**	.521**	.515**	0.81				
PL	.500**	.482**	.489**	.531**	0.82			
AR	.532**	.502**	.511**	.543**	.498**	0.77		
IQ	.557**	.471**	.524**	.545**	.532**	.573**	0.71	
UGC	.502**	.491**	.503**	.520**	.503**	.518**	.539**	0.67

4.16. RESULTS: STRUCTURAL MODEL (HYPOTHESES)

(df = 499, p = 0.002, RMSEA = 0.022, CFI = 0.979, CMIN = 597***, CMIN/df = 1.197, NFI = 0.886)

Table 15

Effects	Estimate	S.E.	P
PL_1 <--- UGC_1	1.234	.129	***
AR_1 <--- UGC_1	1.189	.129	***
IQ_1 <--- UGC_1	1.266	.131	***
BE_1 <--- PL_1	.584	.260	.025
PA_1 <--- PL_1	1.132	.367	.002
IB_1 <--- PL_1	-.605	.782	.439
FP_1 <--- PL_1	.387	.247	.117
BE_1 <--- AR_1	.329	.168	.05
PA_1 <--- AR_1	.050	.134	.709
IB_1 <--- AR_1	.106	.169	.032
FP_1 <--- AR_1	.027	.110	.004
BE_1 <--- IQ_1	.100	.181	.50
PA_1 <--- IQ_1	-.243	.292	.404
IB_1 <--- IQ_1	1.285	.735	.041
FP_1 <--- IQ_1	.392	.207	.05

4.17. MULTIPLE-GROUP MODERATION TEST

Table 16

Regression Weights: (Homophily_high - Default model)

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PL <--- UGC	.193	.083	2.338	.019
AR <--- UGC	.114	.079	1.441	.150
IQ <--- UGC	.146	.082	1.774	.076

Regression Weights: (Homophily_low - Default model)

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PL <--- UGC	.492	.052	9.473	***
AR <--- UGC	.487	.055	8.814	***
IQ <--- UGC	.535	.055	9.669	***

Regression Weights: (Brand_Involvement_high - Default model)

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PL <--- UGC	.266	.056	4.768	***
AR <--- UGC	.223	.055	4.066	***
IQ <--- UGC	.255	.058	4.419	***

Regression Weights: (Brand_Involvement_low - Default model)

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PL <--- UGC	.438	.078	5.633	***
AR <--- UGC	.390	.083	4.694	***
IQ <--- UGC	.439	.080	5.488	***

4.18. SUMMARY OF HYPOTHESES TESTING

Table 17

Hypotheses		Results
1-a	Pleasure is influenced by UGC related to Brand.	Supported
1-b	Arousal is influenced by UGC related to Brand.	Supported
2	Perceived Information Quality responses are influenced by UGC related to Brand.	Supported
3-a	Information Pass-along is positively influenced by Pleasure.	Supported
3-b	Information Pass-along is positively influenced by Arousal.	Not Supported
4	Information Pass-along is positively influenced by cognitive response.	Not Supported
5-a	Impulse buying is positively influenced by Pleasure.	Supported
5-b	Impulse buying is positively influenced by Arousal.	Supported
6	Impulse buying is positively influenced by cognitive response.	Not Supported
7-a	Future-purchase intention is positively influenced by Pleasure.	Not Supported
7-b	Future-purchase intention is positively influenced by Arousal.	Supported
8	Future-purchase intention is positively influenced by cognitive response.	Supported
9-a	Brand engagement is positively influenced by Pleasure.	Supported
9-b	Brand engagement is positively influenced by Arousal.	Supported
10	Brand engagement is positively influenced by cognitive response.	Supported
11	Relationships between consumer internal states and UGC is moderated by Homophily.	Supported
12	Relationships between consumer internal states and UGC is moderated by Brand Involvement.	Not Supported

5. CONCLUSION

Future research can address some of limitations in this research. The proposal was done in a certain context of branded UGC on Facebook page. So, the findings are not generic but context based. The research in future can consider using different context in terms of product or service, social media platform, or different type of social media content; so the model could be changed and validated as per need based on future research. The same research can be done on a broader scale of products. As per the hypotheses analysis, the moderating impact of homophily is found to be significant in terms of influence on online purchase decision making. For the case of brand involvement, the impact in this case or context seems to be insignificant. The findings also show that there are many situational factors that contribute in collective impact on UGC on purchase intention. The main focus of this research is the influence of branded social media content or UGC is a positive aspect. Future research can focus more on the negative aspect of the branded UGC in the same context. Focusing on negative aspects will provide us with more concrete findings. So, future research should focus on negative eWOM in the same context as this research.

REFERENCES

- Accenture. (2013). Retail technology vision 2013. Technology-Vision-2013.PDF. Retrieved from <http://www.accenture.com/SiteCollectionDocuments/PDF/Accenture-Retail->
- Babin, B., Hardesty, D. M., & Suter T., A. (2003). Color and shopping intentions: The intervening effect of price fairness and perceived affect. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(7), 541–551.
- Bagozzi, R. P. (1986). *Principles of marketing management*. Chicago, IL: Science Research Associates.
- Baker, J., Levy, M., & Grewal, M. (1992). An experimental approach to making retail store environmental decisions. *Journal of Retailing*, 68(4), 445–460.
- Bellizzi, J., Crowley, A., & Hasty, R. (1983). The effects of color in store design. *Journal of Retailing*, 59(1), 21–45.
- Bellizzi, J., & Hite, R. (1992). Environmental color, consumer feelings, and purchase likelihood. *Psychology and Marketing*, 9(5), 347–363.
- Brengman, M., & Geuens, M. (2004). The four-dimensional impact of color on shopper's emotions. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 31(1), 122–128.
- Chen, C. Y., Chen, T. H., Chen, Y. H., Chen, C. L., & Yu, S. E. (2013). The spatiotemporal distribution of different types of messages and personality traits affecting the eWOM of Facebook. *Natural Hazards*, 65(3), 2077–2103.
- Comley, P. (2003). Innovation in online research' Who needs online panels? *MRS Research Conference Paper*, 36, 615–639.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Thousand Oaks,

CA: Sage Publications.

- Donovan, R. J., & Rossiter, J. R. (1982). Store atmosphere: An environmental psychology approach. *Journal of Retailing*, 58, 34–57.
- Duffy, B., Smith, K., Terhanian, G., & Bremer, J. (2005). Comparing data from online and face-to-face surveys. *International Journal of Market Research*, 47(6), 615–639.
- Duffy, D. (2005). Affiliate marketing and its impact on e-commerce. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 22(3), 161–163.
- Eroglu, S. A., Machleit, K. A., & Davis, L. M. (2001). Atmospheric qualities of online retailing: A conceptual model and implications. *Journal of Business Research*, 54, 177–184.
- Fiore, A. M., Yah, X., & Yoh, E. (2000). Effect of a product display and environmental fragrancing on approach responses and pleasurable experiences. *Psychology & Marketing*, 17(1), 27–54.
- Google. (n.d.). *Shopper Marketing Agency Council*. (2013). Mobile in-store research. Retrieved from http://ssl.gstatic.com/think/docs/mobile-in-store_researchstudies.pdf
- Heinonen, K. (2011). Consumer activity in social media: Managerial approaches to consumers' social media behavior. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 10(6), 356–364.
- Hovland, C. I., Janis, I. L., & Kelley, H. H. (1953). *Communication and persuasion; Psychological studies of opinion change*. Binghamton, NY: Yale University Press.
- Joinson, A. N. (2008). Looking up or keeping up with people? Motives and use of Facebook. Paper presented at the CHI conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. Florence, Italy. Abstract.
- Kihlstrom, J. F. (1987). The cognitive unconscious. *Science*, 237(4821), 1445–1452.
- Kim, A. J. (2014). Power of consumers: Examining the influence of Brand-related user-generated content on consumer response a dissertation submitted to the faculty of university of Minnesota by Angella.
- Mehrabian, A., & Russell, J. A. (1974). *An approach to environmental psychology*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- Sherman, E., Mathur, A., & Smith, R. B. (1997). Store environment and consumer purchase behavior: Mediating role of consumer emotions. *Psychology & Marketing*, 14(4), 361–378.
- Smith, C. (2014). (n.d.). January 13). *Facebook's Demographics Show Why No Other Social Network Can Match Its Potential for Marketers [Web Log Post]*, 1. Retrieved from <http://www.businessinsider.com/a-primer-on-facebook-demographics-2014-#ixzz2qQrsBYjP>
- Sue, V. M., & Ritter, L. A. (2011). *Conducting online surveys*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Tuten T. L. Valdez, P. & M. A. (1994). (2008). Advertising 2.0: Social media marketing in a Web 2.0 world. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 123(4), 394–409.